

Data-Driven Performance Modeling of Solar Panels Using Polynomial Regression

Fereshteh Jafari^{1,2}, Kamran Moradi¹, Qobad Shafiee¹

¹ Smart/Micro Grids Research Center
Dept. of Electrical Engineering
University of Kurdistan
Sanandaj, Iran

fereshteh.jafari@hevs.ch, k.moradi@uok.ac.ir,
q.shafiee@uok.ac.ir

Fariba Moghaddam²

² Institute of System Engineering
University of Applied Sciences Western Switzerland
Sion, Switzerland
fariba.moghaddam@hevs.ch,

Abstract—Photovoltaic (PV) systems are integral to renewable energy, demanding accurate performance modeling for optimal functionality. This paper presents a pragmatic, data-driven approach employing Polynomial Regression (PR) for solar panel modeling to boost accuracy and adaptability to environmental variables. By emphasizing the advantages of data-driven models in attaining predictive precision, this study aims to reconcile theoretical concepts with practical solar panel performance. PR is employed as a black-box machine learning (ML) algorithm to transcend the limitations of traditional modeling methods, revealing ML's ability to grasp intricate relationships and ensure precise predictions. Utilizing real and simulated datasets encompassing solar irradiance, ambient temperature, and applied load through hardware in the loop (HIL), the model is trained to forecast the electrical outputs of solar panels in two approaches to estimate output voltage and current as well as key points on the panels' I-V curve. Assessment of model accuracy using Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) showcases the PR model's capacity to accurately depict solar panel performance by capturing non-linear relationships between environmental variable conditions and electrical outputs. Experimentation validates the method's effectiveness, focusing on accuracy, generalization to testing, and on-site data validation in two approaches. This research endeavors to bridge the gap between theory and practice, propelling advancements in the field of solar PV systems and facilitating more efficient solar energy utilization.

Keywords—Data-driven modeling, machine learning, polynomial regression, solar panel.

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the necessity for sustainable energy generation is increasingly apparent due to the limitations of energy resources. Renewable energy sources, such as photovoltaic technology play a key role in future energy systems. Efficient use of solar energy is critical, and achieving the maximum power point in photovoltaic panels is essential due to high investment costs and low efficiency. Modeling solar cells/modules based on machine learning (ML) becomes crucial to ensure general performance and optimal outputs under varying environmental conditions [1]. ML algorithms, once trained with a dataset, can autonomously work toward predefined objectives. The overall power of a photovoltaic

panel can be predicted through photovoltaic (PV) panel modeling, but the accuracy of predictions depends on the precision and accuracy of the model. PV panel modeling generally employs mathematical equations and models to estimate the generated power, based on technical characteristics of the panel, solar irradiance, temperature, and other relevant factors. Therefore, while PV panel modeling can predict power reasonably well considering realistic environmental and technical conditions, more accurate predictions can be achieved through real-world testing and measurements [2]. On the other hand, performance prediction has a broader scope and encompasses various aspects of PV panel behavior beyond just power output. Additionally, performance prediction is one of the primary applications of machine learning approaches for solar cell installations. It includes evaluating the overall efficiency and effectiveness of the PV system over time, considering not only power output but also other factors such as voltage, current, and key points of the I-V characteristic curve.

Multiple studies have delved into predicting PV power generation, showcasing varied approaches and performances. [3] and [4] utilize extreme learning machines for power predictions in a Beijing and Jordan PV plant. Also, a Support Vector Machine was applied for PV module predictions [5], in addition, the Multi-Layer Perceptron-based model achieved success even in haze and dust conditions [6], and sunny days [7]. The application of ResNet and white-box models was discussed, showcasing the superiority of black-box models [8] as well as the state monitoring system for PV arrays [9]. Various regression models, each with its RMSE values, were evaluated for short-term electricity predictions [10]. Moreover, Simulink modeling and the application of regression algorithms are shown in [11]. Among regression methods, Gaussian Process Regression was also used in predicting PV module power output [12]. To predict I-V curves under diverse operational conditions, a model was proposed in [13] to predict PV module performance under different operating conditions which used the Power-Law I-V Model by identifying single Diode Model (SDM) parameters. Lastly, a study compared physics-based

and data-driven models, concluding the necessity of data-driven approaches [14], and a comprehensive review of prediction techniques was conducted, emphasizing the drawbacks of some machine learning methods and the advantages of hybrid models [15]. The paper significantly contributes to solar panel modeling and simulation, challenging conventional methods employed in this area.

Current research aims to investigate a practical study of data-driven methods for modeling a PV system. An ML polynomial regression approach is utilized, showing exceptional outcomes rather than relying on complex methods like Support Vector Machine [5], MLP [6], Takagi-Sugeno Fuzzy [16], or Artificial Neural Networks [17]. The models were validated in two distinct regions (Sion/Switzerland and Kurdistan/Iran), employing a Hardware-in-the-Loop (HIL) and NI CompactRIO controller. The main contributions of this paper are outlined as follows:

- Introduce a distinctive approach that emphasizes the importance of acquiring a model representing a solar panel's output voltage and current for variable inputs, vital in the PV industry and critical I-V curve points which precisely reflect the performance of a panel [18], unlike [19-24] which predominantly focused on power output predictions.
- Introduce a groundbreaking methodology with an artificial high persistence of excitation (PE) dataset for model training in contrast to conventional modeling that necessitates prolonged measurements to acquire a suitable dataset.
- Estimate key points from a minimal set of input and output data points accurately. These values form the foundation for studying panels [25], predicting maximum power, and implementing enhanced Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) algorithms.

Unlike [26] and other predecessors proposing fragmented or complex models, this paper provides a holistic and unified model for an entire year which offers a valuable addition to the field of solar panel modeling and simulation.

The paper's structure encompasses five main sections. Section II explores the fundamental characteristics of solar panels, focusing on empirical approaches and machine learning-regression methods. Section III covers data preparation, polynomial regression for modeling, and analysis of key NREL solar panel data. Section IV involves a Case Study, offering practical applications of the model. Section V showcases various voltage and current output scenarios and characteristic curve simulations. At last, the Conclusion consolidates the study's core findings and implications.

II. SOLAR PANEL MODELING

Reviewing different papers in the field of solar panel modeling leads to two groups: white-box modeling and black-box modeling. A white-box approach [27-29] is based on the calculation of parameters I_{ph} , I_c , R_s , R_{sh} , and n as shown in the equivalent circuit of the SDM for a PV module in Fig. 1(a), to determine the current and voltage characteristics and thus the power generation of the PV generator, under different operating

conditions [1]. This model cannot represent the whole manner of the system as it is simple but needs unknown parameters to be calculated continuously for the same model under the influence of radiation and temperature variation [30], leading to a large computational load and time cost. By applying the current-voltage laws, particularly Kirchoff's laws, the relationship between the output current and output voltage of the PV system can be derived as follows:

$$I_c = I_{ph} - I_{sd} \left\{ \exp \left[\frac{V + R_s I_c}{nVt} \right] - 1 \right\} - \frac{V + R_s I_c}{R_{sh}} \quad (1)$$

The black-box modeling, however, does not need any details of the system and will be performed by applying the input data to the system and obtaining the output data as shown in Fig. 1(b). Known as Data-driven, the approach of using data to train machine learning models instead of relying on rules or algorithms designed by humans. In data-driven machine learning, a large volume of data is provided to the model, and the model learns to identify patterns and make predictions based on that data, without knowledge of the structural details of the systems. The data used in data-driven machine learning can come from various sources, including sensors. Typically, data is preprocessed and prepared before entering the model to remove any noise or inconsistencies [31].

Fig. 1. Solar panel modeling: (a) white box modeling by identifying parameters in the equivalent circuit of SDM, (b) black box modeling, using input-output data without knowing panels' details.

In summary, the necessity of using data-driven approaches, the lack of a need for unknown system parameters under all operational conditions, including uncertainty and external disturbances, and online modeling and control with high accuracy and speed are highlighted.

A. Solar Panels Characteristic

The I-V curve of a solar panel illustrates the relationship between the current (I) and voltage (V) output of the panel under different levels of illumination and various load conditions. The shape of the I-V curve depends on the physical characteristics of the PV panel, such as the type of semiconductor material used, the presence of shading or other obstructions, and the temperature and humidity of the environment. Under standard test conditions, with irradiance of 1000 W/m^2 and cell temperature of 25°C , the I-V curve of a PV panel typically exhibits a specific shape known as the *diode curve*. This curve shows that the panel's output current increases with increasing output voltage until it reaches the maximum

power point (MPP). At the MPP, the panel provides the maximum output power for a specific level of irradiance and load. Beyond the MPP, the output current of the panel decreases with increasing output voltage, resulting in reduced output power. This region of the I-V curve is known as the *reverse bias* [32]. Fig. 2 illustrates the I-V curve and output power for a PV module.

Fig. 2. Characteristic curves: I-V and P-V curves of PV modules.

B. Blackbox Modeling

In a data-driven approach, modeling heavily relies on extensive datasets, enabling the model to discern underlying patterns, correlations, and trends for predictive purposes. Unlike traditional physics-based models, black-box models operate without explicit structural equations, allowing them to flexibly adapt to various data patterns in order to make precise predictions [33]. Although these models sacrifice interpretability, they excel in uncovering complex relationships within the data, presenting an efficient means of prediction. Conversely, white-box models, which rely on known model parameters and a predefined structure, often suffer from limitations in accuracy and generalization due to their dependence on specific system conditions [33]. Specifically applied to PV panel modeling, black-box approaches involve constructing a mathematical model based solely on input and output data, without internal insights into the panel's functioning. These models are developed using variables like solar irradiance, panel temperature, and electrical load connected to the panel as input, and the resulting output includes voltage and current produced by the panel. This approach provides a way to model the behavior of the solar panel without explicitly understanding its internal mechanisms, making it highly adaptive to varying conditions and suitable for precise prediction tasks [33].

III. PERFORMANCE MODELING USING PR

Similar to the human learning approach, where some skills are acquired in school through learning from teachers, and other skills are discovered in the environment through our own observations, a machine can also learn in different ways, according to different environments and problem-solving objectives. The choice of machine learning method depends on the type of data, the nature of the problem, and the availability of labeled data. Regression, a supervised learning method, focuses on predicting continuous numerical output (the target) from input features. Supervised learning involves training a

model on labeled data, where each point has a known target value. The model grasps patterns between input features and target values during training, enabling predictions on new, unlabeled data. Different regression algorithms exist, including linear regression (LR), polynomial regression (PR), exponential regression (ER), and support vector regression (SVR) [34]. The advantage of using regression as a machine learning method is its flexibility and ability to handle complex relationships between inputs and outputs. This research employs the simplest machine learning method, polynomial regression (PR) for modeling solar panels. Performance modeling of PV panels involves creating predictive models that estimate the electrical output by examining various factors affecting solar panel performance, such as solar irradiance, temperature, and load conditions, to optimize energy production giving a deep concept of the panel's characteristics.

Three categories of experimental data have been used in this study. The first category consists of artificial data generated in MATLAB/Simulink, while the second category comprises data related to practical testing of the model on solar panels at the University of Kurdistan in Iran, and the University of Applied Sciences Western Switzerland in Switzerland. The third series of data are provided by NREL that were used for modeling the key points of the characteristic curve of the panel using a data-driven method. The flowchart below is used for the performance modeling of PV panels in three general steps. All these steps are implemented in MATLAB/SIMULINK and a brief description of each is discussed in this section.

Fig. 3. Flowchart of the PR Model (PRM) for modeling of the test solar panel.

A. Train Data Preparation

High PE input data is crucial for system identification and modeling using machine learning. This kind of input data holds

varied and diverse features, enabling machine learning models to capture complex relationships and patterns effectively.

The significance of utilizing high PE input data in ML modeling is multifaceted. Firstly, such data bolsters the model's robustness, stability, and adaptability, enabling it to effectively navigate diverse scenarios. Additionally, models trained on this data exhibit better generalization, adeptly predicting outcomes for new or unseen data points. The richness of high PE input data facilitates advanced feature extraction, simplifying the learning process and preventing overfitting by introducing diversity. Furthermore, it equips models to handle complex and nonlinear relationships between input and output, ensuring accurate predictions and enabling informed decision-making for more reliable outcomes [35].

In this study, an artificial dataset with high PE input data was created using limited-range white noise inputs for radiation and temperature, as illustrated in Fig. 4 for panel model training. The method was applied similarly for temperature and load inputs to generate corresponding outputs. These three important inputs significantly affect the performance and behavior of photovoltaic panels, have been considered.

Fig. 4. White noise applied to the panel as radiation input in Simulink.

B. Polynomial Regression

Modeling in a data-driven approach revolves around a large volume of data. The model learns from this data to identify patterns, correlations, and trends that demonstrate the predictive capabilities of the system.

Polynomial regression is a type of regression analysis used for modeling the relationship between independent variables (input) and a dependent variable (output) when the relationship is nonlinear. In the context of modeling a PV panel, multivariate regression can be employed to capture the nonlinear behavior of the output power of the PV panel in response to varying environmental conditions such as solar radiation and temperature.

Unlike simple linear regression, multivariate regression fits a polynomial curve of a specified degree to the data points instead of a straight line. The general equation for PR of degree n is as follows [10]:

$$y = b_0 + b_1x + b_2x^2 + b_3x^3 + \dots + b_nx^n \quad (6)$$

where y is the predicted output (i.e., the output voltage and

current of the PV panel), x is the input feature (i.e., solar radiation or temperature), and b_0, b_1, \dots, b_n are the coefficients of the polynomial terms.

The general equation for PR of output voltage and current of PV is given as:

$$V = b_0 + b_1J + b_2T + b_3R + b_4JT + b_5JR + b_6TR + b_7J^2 + b_8T^2 + b_9R^2 \quad (7)$$

$$I = b_0 + b_1J + b_2T + b_3R + b_4JT + b_5JR + b_6TR + b_7J^2 + b_8T^2 + b_9R^2 \quad (8)$$

where J , T , and R represent solar radiation, panel temperature, and load, respectively. While, b_0, b_1, \dots, b_{11} are coefficients of the polynomial terms, and V and I represent the output voltage and the current of the panel, respectively.

The choice of polynomial degrees in PR determines the model's flexibility in capturing complex patterns in the data. Higher degrees allow the model to fit the data more closely but can lead to overfitting, where the model becomes overly sensitive to noise in the data and performs poorly on new and unseen data. Selecting an appropriate degree is a crucial step in multivariate regression to strike a balance between capturing underlying patterns and preventing overfitting [10].

The design matrix for regression (X) can be expressed separately as:

$$X = [\text{Intercept } J \ T \ R \ JT \ JR \ TR \ J^2 \ T^2 \ R^2] \quad (9)$$

In order to study the accuracy of the model, the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) between the predicted output and the measured values is considered:

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (X_i - X_{pi})^2} \quad (10)$$

where n is the number of data points, X_i represents the actual output values of the PV panel, and X_{pi} represents the predicted output values by the model. RMSE is an important metric to quantify the difference between observed real values and predicted values by a model. This metric provides a measure of the predictive model's error and allows us to gauge how closely the model approximates the real-world behavior of the photovoltaic system. The lower the RMSE value, the better the predictive accuracy of the model.

C. Solar Panel Key Points Modeling

For modeling and estimating key points such as open-circuit voltage, short-circuit current, maximum power point voltage, and maximum power point current in the current-voltage curves of PV panels under different temperatures and irradiance conditions, a second-degree PR is utilized for currents (I_{sc} , I_{MPP}), and a third-degree PR is employed for voltages (V_{oc} , V_{MPP}). The general form of the regression equations is represented as:

$$I = d_0 + d_1J + d_2T + d_3JT + d_4J^2 + d_5T^2 \quad (11)$$

$$V = d_0 + d_1J + d_2T + d_3JT + d_4J^2 + d_5T^2 + d_6J^3 + d_7T^3 + d_8T^2J + d_9J^2T \quad (12)$$

Additionally, the coefficients of the polynomial model for open-circuit voltage, short-circuit current, voltage, and current at maximum power are obtained.

IV. CASE STUDY

The PV system used in this research is two different solar panels with two different objectives of modeling. One is a single-crystal silicon PV module, the 30-watt Blue Solar module, which has been used for modeling in Simulink virtually and for real-world testing of the output voltage and current model. It was employed with data from two different places, Kurdistan/Iran, and Sion/Switzerland as shown in Fig. 5. The specifications of this panel are presented in Table I.

Fig. 5. Test setup: (a) rooftop equipment (b) experimental equipment and online platform in Sion/Switzerland.

TABLE I. THE TEST SOLAR PANEL SPECIFICATION.

Number of Cells	Irr (W/m ²)	Temp (°C)	Voc (V)	Isc (A)	Vmp (V)	Imp (A)	Pmp (W)
36	1000	25	22.87	1.76	18.7	1.61	30

The second selected PV module for this study, from the [36] dataset in Oregon/Eugene, is the single-crystalline silicon PV module (x-Si) model xSi12922 by NREL. The specifications of this panel are presented in Table II. The information provided in this dataset are the data collection time and date, solar irradiance intensity, panel temperature, short-circuit current, open-circuit voltage, maximum output power of the panel, and data related to the voltage and current output curves.

TABLE II. NREL xSi12922 PANEL SPECIFICATION.

Date	Irr (W/m ²)	Temp (°C)	Voc (V)	Isc (A)	Vmp (V)	Imp (A)	Pmp (W)
1/31/2014	1000	24.9	22.06	5.127	17.58	4.724	83.04

V. SIMULATION RESULTS

A. Modeling and Simulation of PV Panels' Voltage and Current Outputs

To test the extracted PR model, the MATLAB/Simulink simulation environment and real measurements with the HIL real-time simulator were used. In order to have a constant irradiance at a fixed temperature with a constant output load for approximately 10 seconds in simulations, white noise with a very small range was applied to the PV panel and variable input resistance. The panel's voltage, current, and power output were

then measured for that irradiance and temperature. The measured voltage and current values from the simulation were considered actual values and compared with the voltage, and current. Electric lower has been obtained from the extracted model by multiplying voltage and current values. The model for the output current and voltage of the 30W panel was tested in two scenarios. Scenario I is done by artificial dataset and scenario II is by real measurements with two different approaches, point-to-point and period testing in two different places.

1) Scenario I

As previously mentioned, the standard test conditions include an irradiance of 1000 W/m² and a temperature of 25°C. Various scenarios were examined (based on the model's training range) to test and compare the model under standard, below-standard, and above-standard temperature, and irradiance conditions.

In the model testing under standard conditions, artificial data was used with an input irradiance of 1000 W/m² with added noise, a temperature of 25 °C with added noise, and an output load resistance of 4.0 Ω with slight noise. The RMSE values of the extracted results for the panel's current, voltage, and power output from the model, compared to the values obtained from simulation in Simulink, are shown in Table III.

TABLE III. RMSE VALUE OF PRM IN STANDARD TEST CONDITION.

Parameter	I	V	P
RMSE	0.0053 A	0.0210 V	0.0042 W

2) Scenario II, in Sanandaj/Kurdistan, Iran

To test the proposed model using the PR method, with a tilt of 35 °C and setting up the online platform, we monitor and record the data at specific time intervals. At this stage, we simultaneously apply the input of irradiance and ambient temperature to the Simulink *PV Array* block in MATLAB and the PRM block. We then compare the results with the actual panel values, which have been implemented with controller NI CompactRIO in the LabVIEW environment through an online platform. The results are shown in Table IV.

TABLE IV. POINT-TO-POINT MEASUREMENTS IN KURDISTAN/IRAN ON AUGUST 22ND & 23RD WITH A TILT OF 35° TO THE SOUTH.

	Inputs	Outputs			
			Simulink	Real	Polynomial Model
1	Irradiance 645W/m ²	Voltage (Open Circuit) (V)	0.4548	0.216	0.127
	Temp 28.8°C	Current (A)	Nan	Nan	Nan
	Date/Time	August 22, 2023, at 9:30 AM			
2	Irradiance 884W/m ²	Voltage (V)	13.56	14.28	12.36
	Temp 36°C	Current (A)	1.519	1.60	1.173
	Date/Time	August 22, 2023, at 11:52 AM			
3	Irradiance 525W/m ²	Voltage (V)	1.92	1.848	1.385

	Temp	27.1°C	Current (A)	0.82	0.86	0.924
	Date/Time	August 23, 2023, at 8:53 AM				
4	Irradiance	607W/m ²	Voltage (V)	1.31	1.368	1.495
	Temp	28.7°C	Current (A)	0.865	0.988	1.068
	Date/Time	August 23, 2023, at 9:20 AM				
5	Irradiance	464W/m ²	Voltage (V)	3.682	3.312	2.442
	Temp	25.6°C	Current (A)	0.864	0.76	0.814
	Date/Time	August 23, 2023, at 8:32 AM				

The relative error for voltage varies from 9.28% to 25.05% and for current varies from 7.10% to 26.68%.

3) Scenario III, in Sion, Switzerland

To test and validate the model, we used the Speedgoat real-time simulator which can be easily connected to MATLAB/SIMULINK. The model is loaded on the simulator and runs every second with the inputs of irradiance, ambient temperature, and load measured through a pyranometer, PT-100, and Ohm's law respectively. To measure, monitor, and save the results, an appropriate platform was made in LabVIEW. The test for validating the model was done for 2 days in September at Sion. In Fig. 6 and 7 the irradiance and temperature are shown for the duration of 5 hours.

Fig. 6. Irradiance measured with a pyranometer for 5h.

Fig. 7. Temperature measured with PT-100 for 5h.

Then the actual voltage and current output of the PV panels are compared with the estimated ones obtained from the model which was implemented with Speedgoat real-time simulator for different periods in a day. In addition, a first-order Butterworth filter is applied to both estimated and actual data. In Fig. 8 and 9, the irradiance and estimated voltage and current results are shown.

In the first test during 27 minutes, one can see that the irradiance varies around 1025 W/m². According to the current and voltage output, the load varied as well in a way that at 13:07, a large change in load amount was observed. (Fig. 8)

Fig. 8. Validation of the developed model: (a) irradiance, (b) measured and estimated voltage, (c) measured and estimated current during 27 minutes.

In the second test (Fig. 9) during 1 hour and 15 minutes, one can see that the irradiance varied according to the sun's position and the time of the day. According to the current and voltage output, the load varied in the first quarter, as well at 13:49, and at 14:28, we had again a large change in load amount and also the reduction in irradiance. During the cloudy weather around 14:00 with irradiance drop, Fig. 9(b) and 9(c) show that the voltage and current model obviously tried to follow the actual output.

The RMSE for the first test is 0.5154 V and 0.1092 A for voltage and current, respectively. And the RMSE for the second test is 0.7673 V for voltage and 0.0573 A for current. It has also been observed that this model does not respond well when the radiation is below 650 W/m² while the sun is going to set, where the importance of sun tracking panels will be felt to receive much irradiance and obtain maximum power.

Fig. 9. Validation of the developed model: (a) irradiance, (b) measured and estimated voltage, (c) measured and estimated current during 1 hour and 15 minutes.

B. Modeling and Simulation of the Key Points of the PV Characteristic Curve

In the test using real data from the NREL, various values of input irradiance and temperature were considered from Dec 2012 to Jan 2014 in Oregon/Eugene with a tilt of 44°C. The results extracted from the PR model were compared with the actual values from the real data as shown in Fig. 10-13.

To assess the model's accuracy, the RMSE between the predicted and measured values is calculated for short-circuit current as 0.0762, open-circuit voltage as 0.2201, and current and voltage at the maximum power point as 0.0736 and 0.2787, respectively, and the maximum power point's RMSE as 1.4382. These values are on 8637 points across varied temperatures and irradiances by PRM.

Fig. 10. Real and predicted open-circuit voltage by the PRM with test dataset by NREL.

Fig. 11. A magnified version of Fig. 10.

Fig. 12. Real and predicted short-circuit current by the PRM with test dataset by NREL.

Fig. 13. A magnified version of Fig. 12.

VI. CONCLUSION

This research aims to contribute to the advancement of photovoltaic panel modeling using the polynomial regression method, providing more accurate and efficient tools for the design, optimization, control, and performance evaluation of photovoltaic systems. In general, modeling has been examined in two approaches: the first approach involves modeling the current and voltage of the 30W panel using artificial datasets and real-world tests in Sion/Switzerland and Kurdistan/Iran, constructing and using input data for model training with high persistence of excitation which makes it unnecessary to collect data over a long period with many sensors which need maintenance processes as well. The second approach involves modeling the key points of the I-V curve, such as short-circuit current, open-circuit voltage, current, and voltage at maximum power, using real-world NREL datasets which give brief

information about the PV panels' characteristics while they are on site. The models in both approaches demonstrated significant accuracy and simplicity due to calculated RMSE between 0.0736 - 0.2787 and 0.0573 - 0.7673 for the first and second approaches, respectively; providing reliable estimates for a wide range of environmental conditions. As we strive towards a cleaner and greener world, it was observed that the integration of machine learning within renewable energy technologies plays a good role in the optimum use of PV systems.

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